

Tunable OTA-C Filter for Biomedical Applications

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ABSTRACT

A novel CMOS continuous time integrated mixed notch and low pass filter is designed for multi standard biomedical applications like ECG, EMG, EEG etc. i.e a single device can be used to monitor multiple bio medical signals. In biomedical signal processing the power line signal (50Hz/60Hz) has to be suppressed with notch filter and remaining low pass band has to be allowed through low pass filter. In this work both notch filter and low pass filter is combined in one schematic. In order to get power line notch filter of 50 Hz and low pass filter of cutoff frequency less than 1 kHz, A Novel Bulk driven Operational Trans Conductance Amplifier (OTA) is used with 0.5V supply in CMOS 130 nm Technology. The transconductance value of proposed OTA is less than 1 nS. In this paper the notch filter of sixth order attained notch depth of 75 dB with 280 nW power consumption and low pass filter of fourth order consumes around 200 nW power.

Keywords— ECG signal, EMG, Notch filter, Operational Trans Conductance Amplifier (OTA), Biomedical

Fig.1 shows the biomedical processing system. It is clear that all bio medical signals consist of very low amplitude with very low frequencies up to 1 kHz [3]. Hence in order to avoid different individual biomedical signal filtering, one can design a simple multi standard biomedical filter for all signals like ECG, EEG or EMG etc. This paper presents a novel multi standard biomedical filter with ultra low power. A notch filter (50/60Hz) [4], [5] has to be needed to avoid power line interface with information signal as it is easily pick up by electrodes.

In this paper a cascaded notch and low pass filters are designed with in a schematic to avoid more area and to avoid extra components and power supply. The designing of ultra low frequency filters is not a simple task because time constant of such filters is around 0.01 s to 1 s range [6], [7]. The time constant of any filter is proportional to RC product but for lower technologies capacitance is limited to 1 pF to 10 pF. In this case capacitance has to be constant so required resistance value should be very high which indicates the effective transconductance(G_m) value should be very low around 1 nS [8], [9].

The G_m value can be reduced by choosing bulk driven in place of gate driven inputs because the transconductance of bulk driven MOS transistors are less than that of gate driven MOS transistors. The effective transconductance can be further reduced by using proposed Operational Trans Conductance Amplifier (OTA) [10], [11]. In this paper Section I describes about introduction. Section II describes about conventional Operational transconductance amplifier design and proposed OTA design. Section III describes about notch filter design and low pass filter design and mathematical analysis of these filters.[12],[13],[14].Section IV describes about simulated results and finally section V describes about conclusion.

I. INTRODUCTION

Now a day's scope of biomedical circuits is increasing tremendously. Basically any biomedical system consists of following building blocks like electrodes, pre-amplifiers, biomedical filters followed by ADC [1]. Basically the biomedical signals ECG (electrocardiogram), EEG (Electroencephalography), EMG (Electromyography) etc., all are having very small amplitude around few millivolts and very low frequency below 1KHz.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of biomedical signal processing system

II. OPERATIONAL TRANSCONDUCTANCE AMPLIFIER DESIGN

In this paper to implement different low pass and notch filters a OTA is used which is designed for ultra low power and low frequency (around 100 Hz) applications. Hence the transconductance value G_m should be very low. In order to get low G_m value, bulk driven OTA schematic is used as shown in Fig. 4. All the transistors used in this OTA are operated in weak inversion (sub threshold) region of operation and while tuning those can be used in saturation region also. Because of wide tuning range and weak inversion region we can attain very low power consumption and bulk driven is chosen to give low G_m value of the order of 50 nS. M1 and M2 transistors are two PMOS transistors to which inputs are given to the bulk terminals. M3 and M4 are NMOS transistors and biased to dc voltage of V_{b2} to act as constant current source. Whereas PMOS transistors M6 and M7 are used as negative resistance to improve the gain of the output response. Finally the transistor M5 and resistors R1 and R2 are act as local common mode feedback of OTA. In this paper 0.5 V supply is used hence the input common mode and output common mode voltages have to be adjusted to half of supply voltage i.e 0.25V. Common mode voltages at outputs can be adjusted by R1 and R2. However by using OTA shown in Fig. 4 can be used to tune from 50 nS to 100 nS. Means the minimum value of G_m value with this OTA is only 50 nS. But in order to get 50 Hz notch G_m value should be very small. Hence in order to reduce G_m value further a proposed transconductor is designed.

A. Proposed Operational Transconductance Amplifier

The bulk driven OTA shown in the Fig. 4 can be tuned only from G_m value of 50 nS to 100 nS. In order to reduce G_m value below 1 nS a bulk driven current deviation OTA with local common mode feedback is proposed in this paper which is shown in the Fig. 3. By using this approach G_m value can be scale down to 10 to 20 times of original G_m value. In this proposed OTA, except M13, M14 transistors all other transistors are operating in weak inversion region to consume low power. The input is given to PMOS transistors M3, M1 and M2, M4 where (W/L) of M1 is less than that of M3 similarly M2 is less than that of M4. For local common mode feedback PMOS transistors M13, M14 are operated in triode region to give a tunable resistance. NMOS transistors M5, M7 and M6, M8 pairs act as constant current mirror. The minimum G_m value by this proposed OTA is around 0.1 nS.

B. Capacitor Multiplier

The capacitor multiplier working is based on the principle of scaling the impedance or admittance from the required port. As capacitance increases, impedance across the capacitor reduces and for particular voltage it will pass more current [5]. This is the basic idea of capacitor multiplier.

Here more current is produced for same voltage, that leads to decrease in impedance and thereby large capacitance is achieved. Capacitor multiplier allows considerable reduction in the area but at the expense of more power. The basic idea of capacitor multiplier using current amplifier is as shown in the fig2

Fig. 2. Capacitance Multiplier

III. MIXED NOTCH - LOW PASS FILTER DESIGN

A. Low pass filter design

In this paper low pass filter and notch filter can be design with similar schematic with a change of input supply positions. With a single ended supply and with two G_m cells a second order low pass filter can be designed as shown in Fig. 4 and with added extra supply a second order notch filter can be designed with the same schematic as Shown in Fig. 3. The response is given by the following equations.

$$\frac{V_o(s)}{V_{in}(s)} = \frac{G_{m1} G_{m2}}{s^2 C_1 C_2 + s C_1 G_{m2} + G_{m1} G_{m2}} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{V_o(s)}{V_{in}(s)} = \frac{G_m^2}{s C_1 C_2 + s C_1 G_m + G_m^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\omega_c = \frac{G_m}{\sqrt{C_1 C_2}} \quad (3)$$

$$Q = \sqrt{\frac{C_2}{C_1}} \quad (4)$$

Equation 1 represents the transfer function of second order low pass filter which is shown in the Fig. 3 Since both the G_m cells are identical $G_{m1} = G_{m2}$ (1) can be reduced to (2) which is in the form of standard second order low pass filter. From the standard second order transfer function (2), the Cutoff frequency can be written as in (3) similarly the Quality Factor of second order low pass filter is given by (4)

response of this mixed notch and low pass is shown in the Fig. 11. In order to compare this paper results with the literature survey, two different comparison tables are given individually i.e Table II for notch filter comparison and Table III for low pass filter comparison with the existing technologies.

Fig. 7. Magnitude response of LPF

Fig. 8. Magnitude Response of sixth order Notch Filter

Fig. 9. Phase Response of Notch Filter

Fig. 10. Magnitude Response of Mixed Notch - Lowpass Filter

Fig. 11. Phase Response of Mixed Notch - Lowpass Filter

TABLE I. COMPARISON TABLE FOR NOTCH FILTER WITH LITERATURE SURVEY

Parameter	Ref[4]	Ref[3]	Ref [2]	Ref[14]	Proposed work
Vdd(V)	1	1	1.8	1.5	0.5
Tech. (nm)	180	180	180	180	130
Zerofreq(Hz)	250	50-250	29-71	40-80	50-60
Notchdep.d	-	50	55	78	75
Order	5	5	5	4	6
Structure	Gm-C	Gm-C	opamp	opamp	OTA-C
Power (nW)	453	458	25000	300	280
THD(dB)	-48	-48	-53	-65	-68
App	ECG	ECG	ECG	ECG,EEG,EMG	ECG,EEG,G,

TABLE II. SUMMARY AND COMPARISONS OF LOWPASS FILTER FROM THE LITERATURE SURVEY

Parameter	Ref[9]	Ref[10]	Ref[12]	Ref[13]	Praposed work
Vdd(V)	3	1.25	0.5	0.5	0.5

Tech.(nm)	180	800	180	180	130
Bandwidth(Hz)	2.4	2000	1M	100	100-1000 (tunable)
Order	6	6	4	2	4
Structure	Gm-C	Gm-C	Gm-C	Gm-C	OTA-C
Power	10 μ W	2.5 μ W	36 μ W	225nW	200nW
THD(dB)	-60	-40	-58	-60	-62
DR(dB)	60	70	54	75	73

V. CONCLUSION

This work presents a novel design of OTA for implementing power line notch filter (50Hz/60Hz) and variable low pass filter with minimum cut-off frequency of 100 Hz and maximum cut-off frequency of 1 kHz for bio potential acquisition systems. After a lot of literature survey this paper has lead to a new approach avoiding demerits of other works with improved characteristics. In this paper a novel bulk driven current sharing Operational Trans conductance Amplifier with local common mode feedback is designed for ultra low power and frequency applications. The total power consumption of the two filters (notch and low pass) is around 480 nW with 0.5 V supply. The Dynamic Range of fourth order low pass filter is 73 dB. Experimental results show significant improvement in power, linearity and total harmonic distortion

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